

An Empirical Study of Purchase influencing factors of Mobile Handset, a Case Study of Pakistan

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Abstract

In recent times the mobile phone industry has revolutionized the world. In fact this modern era is said to be the IT world. From the last decade, It industry and mobile phone handset industry has shown a great progress and it's been continuously progressing up till now. Mobile phone has become a luxury and status symbol more of just a need today. Every person wants a mobile in his hands. Mobile phone industry has also made very much progress now. There are a large number of different brands in market and they are offering a large variety and range of cell phone for almost all income and class people. This research seeks to find out the relationship between the mobile phone buying behavior of consumers and different factors that influence their decisions. First of all the person's demographics are the factors that affect their buying decision or anything else. So for this instance age, gender, marital status and income group of consumers were kept independent variables while type of mobile phone they want to buy or they buy is dependent variable. Different other factors like brand name, features of the mobile, prices of mobiles and social influence while purchasing one was also considered to make the research smooth and easy. A questionnaire on likert scale was formulated and got filled by 200 respondents and a sample of 150 was selected to administer on SPSS.16. Different tests were applied and finally we drew some conclusions. The study suggests that age groups and income groups matter a lot in case of such luxurious purchases. **Keywords:** Age, gender, marital status, income group, brand name, features of the mobile, prices of mobiles, social influence and type of mobile phone.

INTRODUCTION

This study or this research is all about the Demographic Factors that influence the selection of mobile phone handsets in Lahore. Mobile phone today is considered a necessity more of a luxury product. It has made the communication very easy and convenient and has reduced the distances. This communication technology has made this world a Global Village. It allows people to reach others in any part of the world in a very short time. Since its inception in 19th century landlines were serving as the only communication media. Then a large number of technological improvements were made and the invention of cellular phone was a near to the biggest in the line. A tremendous growth was seen in the mobile phone industry within a short time as compared to landline telephone technology. Swedish Mobile first introduced official mobile phone in 1946 and Motorola created first strictly calling "portable cell phone" in 1983 (www.tech-faq.com). The communication dependence on mobile phones increases on almost daily basis and it has become a vital or central communication device of today's world. In recent times the different

mobile phones have a large number of features that are offered to the customers. These features are used to trigger the demand of a particular handset of a particular company. Although almost all the mobile phone companies provides more or less same features with some quality differences. Like big names and brands provide better quality, better services with a premium pricing technique. And others provide with less quality services depending upon the prices they charge. But all of them try to make a differentiation policy amongst others by providing their suitable and affordable services. Mobile phones today are not only used as a need but they have become an imperative part of today's life. Now they are not only served as a mean a communication or communication is no more their fundamental or basic purpose. Today they have become a characteristic or add on the personality of the users of these phones. In spite of provision or offering a rich content or a large number of offers by the mobile phone service providers, there is still a scope to improve the usage of mobile phones in Pakistan for quality services. Sms (short message service) is the most important and value added feature of the mobile phones. It's a very easy and cost effective way of transmitting your messages to anywhere in the world by just a single click. Apart from messages and calls people use their mobile phones for clicking photos, downloading things/ material/ songs/ movies/ wallpapers/ games, uploading their work/pictures/arts, using different applications to sharpen their brains or any other skills, using internet, using social networking sites, signing in, receiving their mails, surfing information and study related material, to improve their vocabulary, playing games, listening songs and many other things. Today they can use these phones to pay their bills, charges, and other dues online through their mobile accounts. And still they expect much more from these devices.

So different people see their mobile phone devices differently and want them in their own way to facilitate them and to make their routine life better anyway like students want their phones to have Microsoft office features, youngsters want their phones to have a color display having latest technological advancements like built in facebook, viber etc.

Human individual characteristics may also affect their liking and disliking. They also trigger the demand for a particular product/feature or may decline for it. Like there can be seen a noticeable difference between the males' and females' choices, likings and disliking. The things/products t that appeals one gender may not be so effective on others' choice. Similarly age has also a powerful impact on the buying decision or behavior of people. People belonging to different age groups have different mind sets regarding their things. For example young generation like style, they want the products showing their style statement and matching with their style. Similarly the aged people are more conscious about quality than having so many useless features in their mobile handsets. Households like having simple e and easy things and devices to use. So it may be said that gender and age differences affect the consumers' choices of their mobile phones.

Genders and age are not the only factors that affect buying behavior. Almost all of the demographics leave a strong impact on buying decision. In this study, we are focused on identifying the factors that influence the consumer buying behavior when they intend to purchase their mobile handsets. These factors have limited to demographic factors only. Demographics include Age, Gender, Income level, Marital Status, Qualification, Education Level, Religion, Birth Rate, Death Rate, Occupation, Family size and so on. But for this study we have taken only 4 of these and they are: Age, Gender, Income and Marital Status.

This research seeks to establish a relationship between these factors and consumer buying behavior regarding mobile phones. Consumer buying behavior or simply buying behavior is an integral part of human behavior and it cannot be separated from it. The research is an empirical type study that

will use a survey or questionnaire method for gathering the data from respondents.

The independent variables for this research will be Age, Gender, Marital Status and Income group while dependent variable is the type of mobile phone handset. Age is defined as the total time period a person has led in this world. It is measured in years. People are grouped according to their age in a number of manners or ways. One is babies, toddlers, infants, juniors, teenagers, young adults, adults, middle-aged, late middle-aged, and elderly. People start using the mobile phones in almost their teenage now. So for this research people ranging from teenage to elders will be considered.

Gender is another important demographic feature. They are only categorized into 2, Male and female. Both these genders have different and opposite characteristics. They behave very different in almost every situation with regard to other like happiness, sorrow, excitement etc. Similarly they can never be indifferent in their buying behavior or in making buying decision. In case of buying the things related to technology, they behave exactly opposite. Males go for advanced technology while females prefer fashion and styles. For the mobile phone sets also gender has a strong impact. Different people belong to different age groups. Some belong to business class while others are salaried persons. Some are qualified professionals and work at their own. Some do white color job and others may perform blue color activities. Further categories may also be done within these groups like salaried peoples' group may have different slabs in which people getting salaries may be divided again. All these things affect their behavior while they intend to make a purchase decision. These all people can be grouped according to classes as well like elite class, upper class, upper middle, lower middle and lower class. A mobile phone has become as necessity for upper class, a status symbol for elite class and the same mobile could be a luxury for lower class. So while a handset their preferences will be different. Low income group will be price sensitive, middle income people will be quality and durability conscious while high income class will desire status, style and brand image while owning a mobile phone.

Marital status, another important factor has a strong impact of the type of mobile phone. Singles want mobile sets as a need or just for using it in urgent times. They are actually cost conscious. While married people may have different preference or thinking. They might want to owe a phone better than anybody in their social circle or vice versa for both.

So it is known people are different, their personalities, traits, thinking and behaviors are different. Everybody has a different perception of their world, their things so as a mobile phone. So this research seeks to explore the differences among different people while having a mobile phone. This study seeks to know the relationship among our dependent and independent variables here.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

People are always different from one another. They are of different nature, behavioral characteristics, moral values, thinking styles, stamina, perceptions etc. They come from very different and unique mind sets. Not even a single brain resembles to other so there approaches also differs in different scenarios. This does not mean that people or individuals are that much different that they can't even show same behaviors. Thousands of people around the globe may act indifferently in fact they do but these acts are also influenced by their different thinking styles and approaches of life. Same is the case with "consumers". "Consumer" has been very important for the marketing and much research has been conducted to know about their behaviors. For this they have concluded different things as per their results. As this research seeks to know the factors influencing mobile handsets purchase so it also has to do with consumer characteristics and buying

behaviors. For this research paper demographics are taken as key variables so different researches regarding consumers' age, gender, marital status and income groups will be considered as a starting point. "People do not buy just anything at all but things that will bring value to them and those that they attach good image. Gender roles are the behaviors that are viewed as being appropriate for males and females in society." (Forbes, 2012).

Gender can play an important role in making any purchase or purchase decision of any good. Gender can also affect the decision in case of a mobile phone because today mobiles are equally used by the female members of our society and they are equally keen to adopt the new technology and trends in this field. Proving this point Atkin et al. (2007) concluded that women were more keen or interested or they were seen more likely to get the information regarding their thing from store people (sales staff or store personnel), price tags, shelf tags, written description given with the things, while men liked getting more information regarding things through reading books. It was also reported by the same that women seem to be more careful during purchase or shopping regarding the products as compared to men. They are not that careful. Women can spend or they want to spend very much time in the marketplace in gathering data and information about their desired products. They can spend time just to satisfy themselves regarding the product but men are different. They do not like spending much time in market so they just prefer to buy the things that are easily available to them. Atkin et al. (2007) also suggested that such as medals, price and brand name are used by female consumers as risk reduction strategies. Similar studies were performed in Australia and New Zealand and they concluded that females utilize the label style or design to a greater extent than males (Mueller & Lockshin, 2008).

Gender can also be used for differentiation and market segmentation policies. Even genders can be used as a target market for any specific product. Just as the genders are different, so as their perceptions and buying preferences. It is not only seen for other products but same is the case with mobile phones. Females want easy to use and easy to carry mobiles while men want their desires apps and features in whatever size or shape etc. Josiassen, Assafi, and Karpen (2011) Suggest that Age, gender and income influence the type of product or service one will consume and marketers should segment the market and produce to suit their target market. Funk and Ndubisi (2006) found a strong connection or relationship between the color and the choice of an automobile. The study further identified the gender affect on that relationship as well. Another study by Dittmar et al in 1996 argues in the favor of this point that men and women buy and relate things with different logics and reasons. Darley and Smith in 1995 stated that men and women are subject to different social pressures. And this pressure can be seen in their buying behavior. Their purchase decisions are more often influenced by their situations, positions and the pressures they get from their people. Meyers and Levy in 1988 presented the same point of gender differences by arguing that males are generally self-focused while women see both, themselves and others and this is also seen in their purchase behaviors. Coley and Burgess (2003), also in their empirical study on wide range of products such as clothing, consumer electronics and books etc. had found significant differences between men and women with respect to both affective and cognitive process components.

Singh, May 2009 also made a research in India about the buying behavior of mobile handsets of different age and gender groups and he found and concluded that Indian women were less aware about the technical aspects of mobile sets or with the core technical features so physical appearance was more important for them than any other features while men focused primarily on these value added and technical features. Another thing he found was female side was not that much interested about the "brand" while men paid attention to the brand of their cell phones. Similar point was

proved by another research made by Saif et al, 2012 in Pakistan. This research was also about different factors affecting consumer buying behavior and it concluded that the females respondents were not very well aware of technological advancements in mobile industry as compare to men so men paid particular attention towards advance technology and features in their mobile sets while women did not bother those new/advanced features much. So all the above discussion has proved that there is a significant difference among the buying behavior of different gender groups> It may be due to any reason but it is to be prove now in this research.

Apart from gender, “age” also plays a crucial role in the selection of any product or thing especially in case of the technology related items like cellular phones, laptops etc. Much research has also been conducted on that topic and different results were found and concluded. Like as discussed earlier Singh, May 2009 made his research on the mobile handsets buying behavior of different age and gender groups”. He found in his research that different age groups have different buying perceptions and preferences in case of mobile phones. Age groups of 18-30 were found less price sensitive than the age groups of 50 or above. He concludes that the people between 18-30 pay more attention towards brand name, brand image, advanced technology and features than price while the people belonging to 50 or are less attractive to these post purchase service and features. According to another research by Barak and Gould (1985), they suggest that the younger consumers are more interested in trying new products and new technologies as compared to the older ones. Similarly younger customers are more willing to buy new and stylish products as compared to older. They want to get and try new stylish products and remain up to date. They are seen to be more interested in obtaining information about those things than others.

This all discussion concludes that there is a significant impact of age on the consumers’ shopping and their buying behaviors. The purchase of mobile has become a style statement more of a necessity that’s why its purchase is also influenced by a lot of factors. Top of them are age and gender. Because all age groups have different preferences and perceptions regarding their things. As well both the genders take these technology related devices differently and behave accordingly. And much research has previously taken place on these topics and they have summed up these things. Now next factor that influences or that may influence your mobile handset is income level. Income is also considered a very important factor during the purchase decision of anything. If it’s the case of a necessity cum luxury then it becomes more important. People belonging to different income groups or different income level act differently in different situations and they perceive things in different manner. Same thing can be a necessity for some while it can be a luxury for some at the same time while some can take it as a mere wastage of money and time as well.

Juwaheer, 2014 made a research about the mobile preferences of young customers in Mauritius and he concluded that the young customers give great emphasis on the price, brand name and features of a mobile phone. He found the price to be the most influential factor for the buying decision of mobile industry for youngsters as they used to have limited pocket or income. George Aboagye Agyeman, 2013 concluded in his research that the income level of the consumer is a vital determinant for the purchase of a mobile phone and the educational level also influence the type of mobile phone to buy or use and due to this manufacturers cannot ignore it. Yang et al, 2007 found in their research that the students and non-students US consumers are price focus and sensitive. They try to have low priced mobile phone while Chinese customers focus on features more than the price. Dr Das, 2012 concluded that the people in India are price sensitive and they want their phone new and advanced features but low cost as their income levels are not that high.

Marital status is also an important factor that may influence on the type of phone you own. To

prove all the above mentioned points, now we will conduct a research having questions regarding all o these factors.

THEORATICAL FRAMEWORK:

For this research the dependent variable is the type of mobile handset a person buys or intends to buy. The dependent variable depends upon these 4 factors/variables for this study. That means these 4 are the factors actually that triggers the purchase of a mobile handset for a person. These are the factors that may or may not be the reason for a particular type of a cell phone purchase decision.

- Gender of the buyer,
- Age of the buyer,
- Income Level/Group to which the buyer belongs,
- Marital Status

The type of mobile handset one selects or intends to have is a dependent variable in this study and it is based on the age, gender, income group of the buyer and his/her marital status.

Age is the first independent variable for the ongoing research. Age of the buyer, customers or potential customers influences their liking/disliking and their perceived quality and features in the mobile phone. People belonging to different age groups respond differently to different mobile sets and brands. This variable was tested through many researches and it is taken here from “Mobile Handset Buying Behavior of Different Age and Gender Groups” by Juwaheer et al in May,2009, Gender is the second independent variable in this study. Many different research and studies were also done on this as well. It is based on “Mobile Handset Buying Behavior of Different Age and Gender Groups” by Juwaheer et al in May, 2009,

Income group is the third independent variable in this study. It is taken from “An Empirical Study of Consumer Behavior in Mobile Phone Market in Bhutan” by Dr. L. Shashikumar Sharma in 2010, This variable was taken from the study “Demographic and Geographic Influence of the Country-

of-Origin Image on Consumer Purchase Decision” by Anwar et al in 2013 in Pakistan,

METHODOLOGY:

Do the demographics influence the type of Mobile Phone/Handset a person possess or intends to? Does the age of buyer or potential buyer influences the type of mobile phone he would have?

- Does the gender of buyer have any impact on the selection of cellular phone?
- Does the type of mobile handset is influenced by the income level a person belongs to?
- Is there any impact of the marital status on the purchase of a cell phone?

H1: There is a significant relationship between the age of the buyer and the type of mobile phone he buys or uses.

H2: There is a significant relationship between the gender of the buyer and the type of mobile phone he buys or uses.

H3: There is a significant relationship between the income level of the buyer and the type of mobile phone he buys or uses.

H4: There is a significant relationship between the marital status of the buyer and the type of mobile phone he buys or uses.

This study is based on the exploratory or descriptive research design as it seeks to establish or explore the relationship between the dependent and independent variables mentioned above. The research is undertaken in the form of survey. A questionnaire is developed about all the key independent variables to check out their individual impact on the mobile phone selection process. This is the primary as well as secondary type of research. Time horizon for this study is cross sectional. The study area for this research is Lahore, the capital of Punjab province of Pakistan. Lahore is highly populated city of Pakistan and majority of the people here use the mobile phones. And it would be easier and convenient to get the questionnaires filled here and to extract the information on this research.

The study population for this study is also the regular mobile phone users as it was needed to get the correct and accurate results. Total population of Lahore is more than 10 million and more than a 50% is the mobile phone users.

The sampling technique for this study is non probability sampling. The respondents are selected according to the ease of access and their willingness to take part in the survey because of the shortage or time limitation and limited resources. Sample size for this study is 200. 200 questionnaires were got filled for the respondents.

The instrument used for data collection was questionnaires method. A questionnaire is developed to get the information from the respondents from the selected areas. The questionnaire is closed ended and is based on Likert Scale Type. Likert Scale gives the respondents 5 options to choose from them. The questionnaire was based on 3 major sections. First section or 1st table is based on demographics of the respondents. These are asked to quantify the results. Then dependent variable (The type of mobile phone handset) is mentioned. The second section is based on screening question. This question is here to make sure that the respondents do possess their own mobile phone or phones. The third section is based on the questions which are grouped under different heads to quantify the results and make them easy for respondents. The heads were Brand Name, Price, Features and Social Influence. These 4 heads can be taken as dependent variables to find out the impact of independent variables [Age, gender, marital status and income group] upon them.

Data analysis was done through research software, SPSS version 16. Different statistical tests and measures were applied to get the results out of the data collected from respondents. Reliability test was administered to check the reliability of the data. Cross tabulations, Bar charts, Regression, Correlation analysis was performed to find out the relationships between different variables. Stem and Leaf charts and Box plot diagrams were also drawn to find out final results and conclusions.

DATA ANALYSIS:

This research was conducted through questionnaire method. A questionnaire was constructed according to the dependent and independent factors. It was got filled by 150 respondents. These respondents include people from both the genders, male and female and of both marital statuses. They were grouped into different age categories starting from 15 years ending so forth. Different occupations were mentioned to know the field of work of those respondents along with their income groups. Different income groups were made to categorize them. These income groups were ranging from “less than 20,000 PKR” to “more than 100,000 PKR.” These filled questionnaires were administered through SPSS version 16. Tables, charts and different graphs were generated to find out their results and data analysis. Demographics were compared with one another through crosstabs and bar charts while the dependent independent variables were checked through regression correlation and box plot diagrams.

Reliability Analysis:

Table 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.604	4

Cronbach's Alpha is basically used to measure the internal consistency of the data. It is referred to as the degree of consistency. It is used to measure the reliability or internal consistency. When Cronbach's Alpha is increased or greater, then the inter correlation among the tem also increases and is thus known as internal consistency and itestimate the reliability of test score items. The reliability coefficient, Cronbach's a (Cronbach, 1951), is generally used to test the reliability of a scale. A value of 0.604 is greater and is deemed to be indicative of an acceptable reliability. The Cronbach's alpha for the items is 0.604 suggesting that all the items are reliable.

Regression analysis is done to find out the impact of independent variables on the dependent variables in any study or research. In other words it is used to predict the value of dependent variable with the help of one or more independent variables. A mathematical equation or expression is used to find out its value.

For a single independent variable:

$$Y = a + bx$$

For multiple independent variables:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + \dots + b_nX_n$$

In these equations, y is referred to as dependent variable whose value depends upon the independent variables. X or X1, X2, X3etc are the independent variables of this regression equation. B are their coefficients or multiples, they are here to limit the effect of any individual independent variable on

the dependent one. While “a” is constant and it will be the value of dependent variable in case all the independent variables are zero.

In this research there are 4 independent variables and they are Age, Gender, Marital Status and Income Group of the respondents while to quantify the results the dependent variables are also divided under 4 heads and these heads are dependent variables for this study. These dependent variables are Brand Name, Features of mobile phones, Price factor and Social Influence.

Table 2
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.249 ^a	.062	.036	.755

a. Predictors: (Constant), Income Group, Gender, Age, Marital status

Table 3
ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.441	4	1.360	2.389	.054 ^a
	Residual	81.997	144	.569		
	Total	87.438	148			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Income Group, Gender, Age, Marital status

b. Dependent Variable: BRAND NAME

Table 4
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.660	.280		13.057	.000
	Gender	.111	.125	.072	.887	.377
	Age	-.085	.089	-.122	-.958	.340
	Marital status	-.190	.215	-.116	-.885	.378
	Income Group	-.004	.052	-.009	-.081	.936

a. Dependent Variable: BRAND NAME

Here Y is Brand name, dependent variable whereas X1 is Gender, X2 is Age, X3 is marital status and X4 is Income group. A is 3.660 for this regression equation which is constant. Highest coefficient for this equation is of Gender which means the highest complexity is of gender which 11.1%. That shows gender has the largest impact on brand name while purchasing a mobile. Other three variables have negative complexity that means they don't have that much impact on brand name. After gender comes Income group. Its complexity is -0.4%. It means if you belong to low income group the less impact will be there on brand name of your mobile. The ratio of marital status and Age is -19% and -8.5% respectively.

R squares for this equation is 6.2% and it shows that there is a variation of 6.2% in dependent variable prediction by independent variables while the adjusted R2 is 3.6%. The difference between R2 and adjusted R2 is 2.6% which is not that high. It means if we take the whole population instead of this sample, the results may vary up to 2.6% from now.

The f-static is 2.389% which a [p value= 0.054] that shows the independent variables do not have sufficient or strong impact on this dependent variable. The significance level for independent variable is 4% here. This significance level shows that the model is effective for linear regression.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS:

Correlation analysis is done to find out the relationship between 2 defined variables. One is dependent and the other is independent. Following is the correlation analysis of all 8 factors, dependent and independent. Independent variables are Age, gender, marital status and income group while dependent variables are Brand name, features, price and social influence.

Table 5

		Correlations							
		BRAND NAME	FEATURES	PRICE	SOCIAL INFLUENCE	Gender	Age	Marital status	Income Group
BRAND NAME	Pearson Correlation	1	.418 ^{**}	.141	-.003	.104	-.225 ^{**}	-.222 ^{**}	-.168 [*]
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.088	.970	.207	.008	.008	.040
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
FEATURES	Pearson Correlation	.418 ^{**}	1	.289 ^{**}	.001	-.052	-.115	-.022	-.023
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.001	.994	.529	.183	.785	.782
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
PRICE	Pearson Correlation	.141	.289 ^{**}	1	.091	-.122	.125	.108	.119
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.088	.001		.288	.137	.127	.195	.148
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
SOCIAL INFLUENCE	Pearson Correlation	-.003	.001	.091	1	.202 [*]	.092	.089	.058
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.970	.994	.288		.013	.282	.404	.478
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Gender	Pearson Correlation	.104	-.052	-.122	.202 [*]	1	-.133	-.128	-.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.207	.529	.137	.013		.104	.124	.144
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Age	Pearson Correlation	-.225 ^{**}	-.115	.125	.092	-.133	1	.742 ^{**}	.623 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	.183	.127	.282	.104		.000	.000
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Marital status	Pearson Correlation	-.222 ^{**}	-.022	.108	.089	-.128	.742 ^{**}	1	.638 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008	.785	.195	.404	.124	.000		.000
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Income Group	Pearson Correlation	-.168 [*]	-.023	.119	.058	-.120	.623 ^{**}	.638 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.040	.782	.148	.478	.144	.000	.000	
	N	149	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Their tabular form is presented above that is showing the combinations and closeness of different variables with one another. Their one by one detailed explanation and analysis is given below:

RESULTS:

From the data analysis, conclusion and findings explained above, we have drawn some final results. According to the research, detailed study and articles, we found that demographics have an impact on the purchase of mobile phone handsets. Our final dependent variable was “the mobile handsets you buy or want to buy”. In order to quantify and justify our results, we divided the dependent variable into 4 heads of questionnaire and they were used as dependent variables for analysis later as well.

We found that the gender and age are the variables that mostly affect the decision of purchasing a mobile phone. Females were found more brand conscious compared to males. Age group of 15 to

30 majorly belonged to their student life and they were single. They showed more enthusiasm in almost all field. They were found brand conscious but on the other hand they were price conscious too. People of age 61 or more disagreed with brand. They were not really fond of brands and disliked the concept. All the age groups were conscious for the features of their brands but most of all were from the age of 41-50 years. All income groups were price conscious. All income groups were features conscious as well. Social influence was the dependent variable that had the least relationship or closeness with independent variables. Features and Brand name were the variables majorly affected by independent variables. Price was also hit by almost all age groups, income groups, gender groups and marital statuses.

FINDINGS:

First of all the relationships between demographics were seen and analyzed through bar charts and cross tabulations. From this analysis we got these results:

- There were total 149 respondents for gender age cross tabs out of which men were 79 and women were 70. Majority of the respondents fell into the 1st age group ranging from 15 to 30. 22 belonged to 31-40 age groups. 6 were from 41-50. 10 were from 51-60 and 6 were from 61 or above.
- Next was gender*marital status. Single respondents were 102 while married were 48.
- Next was gender*income groups. According to that total 66 respondents were from first income group. 34 were in second and 15 were in third income group. Fourth and fifth group had 4 and 14 respondents respectively.
- Next was gender*occupation crosstabs. 66 respondents were students. 60 were employees and 13 house wives were also surveyed. 10 belonged to any other category.
- Next was age*marital status. Total 105 respondents were of 15 to 30 out of which 98 were single and 7 were married. Total 22 were in 31 to 40 and 4 were single while 18 were married. Total of 7, 10 and 6 respondents fell in last 3 categories respectively and all were married. Total 102 people were single while 48 were married that shows a major part of this study was consisted of single aging from 15 to 30.
- Next cross tabulation was of age and income groups. Total 66 people came into 1st income group. Total 35 came into 2nd income group. 16 candidates came into the 3rd income group. Total 15 respondents came into 4th income group. 5th income group consisted of 4 people. Last income group had 14 people.
- Next was age*occupation. According to the summary table total 66 were students, 61 were employed, 13 were house wives and 10 belonged to any other category.
- The next cross tab was of marital status and income group. According to the findings there were total 64 singles and 2 married people belonging to 1st income group. 24 singles and 11 married were in 2nd income group. Total 16, 8 each marital status people belonged to third income group. 3 singles and 12 married were in 4th income group. 1 single and 3 married were in 5th group while 2 singles and 12 married were in last income group. .
- The next analysis is of marital status and occupation. . Total 102 singles filled the questionnaires and their respective distribution was as 66, 32, 0 and 4 in those occupation categories. Total 48 respondents were married and they fell in the last three occupation groups only. Their bifurcation was as 29, 13 and 6 respondents in last three categories. No student was found married.

- This last bar chart was the cross tabulation of income group and occupation groups. 66, 61, 13 and 10 are the totals of people falling in all occupation categories respectively. 66, 35, 16, 15, 4 and 14 are the totals of people of all income groups respectively.

Then a regression analysis was done for dependent independent variables and we got:

- Gender had the largest impact on brand name while purchasing a mobile. Other three variables have negative complexity that means they don't have that much impact on brand name.

- R squares for this brand name was 6.2% and it shows that there is a variation of 6.2% in dependent variable prediction by independent variables while the adjusted R2 is 3.6%. The difference between R2 and adjusted R2 is 2.6% which is not that high. It means if we take the whole population instead of this sample, the results may vary up to 2.6% from now.

- When "features of mobiles" was kept as dependent variable, we found highest complexity coefficient of marital status and then income group. Age and gender was negatively related.

- It difference in R2 and adjusted R2 was 2.7% only.

- When "price" was kept as the dependent variable, highest complexity was of Age. Means age matters in case of price of mobile phones. After comes Income group. Gender and marital status had negative beta.

- Its difference of R2 and adjusted R2 was again 2.7% only means variation from results would be 2.7% only.

- When "social influence" was kept as dependent variable, we got the highest coefficients of gender. Age stood second. Then marital status and income group came respectively.

- It difference in R2 and adjusted R2 was 2.6% only.

After that a correlation analysis was done. It was done to find closeness of variables and we got following results:

- Total 16 hypotheses were made for correlation analysis, 4 for each independent variable as there were 4 dependent variables as well.

- Hypothesis 1 stated that there is no relationship between gender and brand name.

- Hypothesis 2 stated that there is a relationship between age and brand name.

- Hypothesis 3 stated that there is a relationship between marital status and brand name.

- Hypothesis 4 stated that there is a relationship between income group and brand name.

- Hypothesis 5 stated that there is no relationship between gender and features of mobile phone.

- Hypothesis 6 stated that there is no relationship between age and features of mobile phone.

- Hypothesis 7 stated that there is no relationship between marital status and features of mobile phone.

- Hypothesis 8 stated that there is no relationship between income group and features of mobile phone.

- Hypothesis 9 indicated that there is no impact of gender on the price of a mobile phone

- Hypothesis 10 indicated that there is no impact of age on the price of a mobile phone

- Hypothesis 11 indicated that there is no impact of marital status on the price of a mobile phone

- Hypothesis 12 indicated that there is no impact of income group on the price of a mobile phone

- Hypothesis 13 stated that there is a significant impact of gender on social influence.

- Hypothesis 14 stated that there is no impact of age on social influence.

- Hypothesis 15 stated that there is no impact of marital status on social influence.
- Hypothesis 16 stated that there is no impact of income group on social influence.

LIMITATIONS and RECOMMENDATIONS:

Some recommendations are there for this kind of study:

- This kind of study needs more time and detailed research.
- People or respondents should be willing to give information or respond to the survey. It was a difficult task gathering data from this large number of people.
- This kind of study needs more paper work, detailed analysis which was not possible due to time shortage.
- The study needs to be more precise and detailed.
- Availability of related material should be made easy for conducting the research or thesis work.
- The study population should be more different and large which was not possible due to the shortage of time and resources.

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